

SIMILAR AND DIFFERENT FEATURES OF VERBAL EXPRESSION IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK COMMUNICATION

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ABSTRACT

The article focuses on the comparison of distinctive features of verbal expressions, their similar and dissimilar peculiarities in English and Uzbek communication. The examples are provided in the English and Uzbek languages concerning culture specific verbal expressions. In this study we also mention some of researcher's work, such as the contribution of Uzbek scholar to the study of verbal means in Uzbek communication.

Key words: communication, verbal communication, verbal means, verbal expressions, culture, polite, feeling;

It must be mentioned that communication is regarded as an essential part of our life with a view to operating our life and opening way in relationships. In almost all cases information sent by people is orally or in writing which refers to verbal communication. Uzbek communication style has its specific features. For example, Uzbek people are usually indirect at times while communicating and there are many underlying meanings one has to pick up on. Similarly, the English are more indirect than overly direct. In most cases, state of being blunt is considered impolite. Therefore, it is worth considering the tone of voice as well as facial expression as to indicate what is really being conveyed.

The English word for expressing thankfulness for someone is "Thanks" and "Thank you". However, the first is slightly less formal than the latter. The Uzbek word "Rahmat" can be utilized as "Thanks" in many circumstances. If the English are thankful, they normally use "Thanks", "Cheers", "Thanks a lot", without doubt relying on context. One of the utmost features of Uzbek culture is that old people say and wish the helper some good pleasant words.

In the Uzbek language, for example, one may hear such wishes if they help someone old, such as "Umringiz uzoq bo'lsin" means "May you live long life", "Barakah toping", "Baxtli bo'ling" means "Be happy". Nonetheless, these kinds of wishes are usually said in special occasions of English culture.

In addition, the death of a person is seen as a shocking state for those who are close to the dead. So informing the family members or close ones is not an easy situation. For instance, in Uzbekistan it depends on its regions. Such expressions as “vafot etibdi”, “qazo qilibdi” are replaced instead of saying “o‘lib qolibdi” as a way of avoiding direct information. Similarly, this situation in English can be expressed with “pass away” (o‘tib qolmoq – on as we have seen in Uzbek) and “die” (“o‘lmoq” in Uzbek) in which the latter is viewed a bit impolite in both English and Uzbek.

Apart from this, the Uzbek culture is known as being hospitable, so there are also several verbal expressions for welcoming people in Uzbekistan. The expression is “Xush kelibsiz” and the response to it is “Xush ko‘rdik” in Uzbek. Similarly, it is “You are welcome” and “It is nice to see you here” in the English language. The hospitality of the Uzbek is also seen in welcoming for their traditional meal Pilaf. In this regard, it can be perceived as a kind of platform, for business communication, where people can briefly discuss matters[1, P-20].

In terms of the way of asking apology or grabbing one’s attention, it should be mentioned that they do differ across cultures. For instance, in attracting one’s attention or asking how to reach a destination “Excuse me” is used that is “kechirasiz” in Uzbek. If someone makes a mistake or asks to forgive the Uzbek say “Uzr” and it is “Sorry” in English.

The other verbal expression used in an Uzbek family while sitting around a table for a meal is “Yoqimli ishtaha” by members of the family who say to each other as soon as they begin having a meal, while “Bon appetit” and “Enjoy your meal” can be used in English in such case. “Bon appetit” is a French phrase that was adopted in English. The use of this phrase and telling somebody to enjoy their meal is very popular. This phrase can also be said by a guest.

After a meal the Uzbek, especially the elderly, do not stand up without making a dua. The Uzbek often teach their children how to say or do “ameen” from the very beginning of their childhood following their religion, Islam. After a meal both in English and Uzbek they may compliment the person who prepared the meal, its taste or the variety served. Uzbek people may say “Qo‘lingiz dard ko‘rmasin”, “Mazali bo‘libdi”, whereas in English such verbal expressions can be used “Thank you for having me”, “I loved the dinner”, “We thoroughly enjoyed ourselves” and so on.

To sum up all the points above, it is worth taking a little time to think about the differences between the English and Uzbek with their verbal expressions reflecting culture. The usage of euphemistic expressions in our speech in both cultures shows our politeness to the participants in communication. From the given examples, we conclude that there are some verbal expressions with the same meaning in both languages, whereas a word is enough or even its equivalent cannot be found in the other.

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